

Tunneling Fundamentals, Practice and Innovations

Annual Short Course

Special Session on University Transportation Infrastructure

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Operational Resilience of Traffic Tunnels

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Outline

- Introduction/Background
- Literature
- Research Objectives
- Methodology
- Tunnel Data Collection
- CDOT Tunnel Database
- Eisenhower Tunnel Data
- Systematic Quantifiable Data
- Module Development Methodology
- Summary and Future Work
- Acknowledgements

Introduction – Road Tunnel

Importance

- **Efficient Solution** to Transportation needs
- **Expensive Asset** to build and maintain
- Network - **Dependence** on Tunnels

Requirements

- **Functional Continuity**
- **Recovery** from **Events**

Tunnel Functionality

- **Through-pass capacity** over time.

Hindrance

- **Disruptive Events**

Eisenhower Tunnel, Colorado

Introduction : Tunnel Design

Engineering Goal

- **Optimize** - maximize through-pass capacity

Improvements

- Using **Experience** from major Disruptive Events
- **Advanced technologies** (detectors, alarms, sensors, etc.)

Past Knowledge

- **Not systematic** and is extracted **case – by – case**
- Lack of uniform practice in tunnel data collection

Smoke & Fire Detection System, Gotthard tunnel

Sprinkler System, Stockholm Bypass tunnel

Some Major Functionality Loss Events

Tunnel	Tunnel type	In service since	Date of event	Incident	Closure time	Cost* (million \$)	Casualty (and injury)
Sasago tunnel, Japan	Uni-Directional	1977	12/2/2012	Ceiling collapse	68 days	Not available	9 (2 injured)
Mont Blanc, France and Italy	Bi-directional	1965	3/24/1999	Vehicle fire	~3 years	481	39
Gotthard road tunnel, Switzerland	Bi-directional	1980	10/24/2001	Accident / fire	~2 months	14	11
Big-dig tunnel, I-90 connector tunnel, USA	Uni-Directional	2000	7/10/2006	Ceiling collapse	6 months	34	1
Tauern tunnel, Austria	Bi-directional	1975	5/29/1999	Fire	3 months	26	12 (49 injured)
Caldecott, USA	3 tubes	1964	4/7/1982	Collision / Fire	6 weeks	3	7 (2 injured)
Holland, USA	2 tubes, Uni-Directional	1927	5/13/1949	Goods falling / fire	3 days / partially closed for 3 months	0.6	1 (66 injured)

Smaller but Frequent events are not represented in the Literature

Motivation

- Lack of Systematic Quantifiable data collection
- Decision making not related to Tunnel Functionality
- Analysis of trend and severity of Events

Questions of Interest to Tunnel Owners

- For a given tunnel design, what does the **best and worst-case scenario function loss** one can expect, given certain disruptive conditions?
- Are there certain tunnel types, design, or management practices, **that will increase or mitigate tunnel vulnerability** from such functional interruption? If so, by how much?

Research Objective

I. Tunnel Data Collection Framework

Develop a uniform data collection framework for road tunnel that will support quantitative analysis of tunnel resilience.

II. Probabilistic Simulation Tool Development

Develop a stochastic event simulation model/tool to quantitatively predict road tunnel downtime and resilience given tunnel parameter inputs.

III. Sensitivity Studies

Conduct a parametric sensitivity study using the prediction model results to find out the relationship between critical events and tunnel functionality.

Methodology

Tunnel Data Collection Framework

Preliminary Framework

Design, Construction and Management Practices and Data Collection

- FHWA Technical manual
- TOMIE manual (O & M)
- SNTI (Specification for Tunnel inventory)
- Road Tunnel Manual (PIARC)

Establish a Tunnel Data Structure

- Static
- Dynamic
- Function

Preliminary Data Collection Framework

Tunnel Data Collection

Collect and Study Data

- Major Tunnels in the US
- Eisenhower (EJMT) Tunnel Logs – CDOT
 - ❖ 1 year data log
- Access to CDOT database
 - ❖ IBM Cognos
 - ❖ Event Audit Reports
- Request Data from Tunnel Owners

State	State Code	# of tunnels
California	6	9
Colorado	8	4
Virginia	51	11
Massachusetts	25	7
New York	36	4

State Wise Major Tunnel Owners

COLORADO DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION EJMT TUNNEL OPERATIONS LOG					FAN OPERATIONAL STATUS																Crew: "B"		
Day : Mon.	Traffic Count		CO Reading		North Tunnel								South Tunnel										
Date: 08.7.17	North Tunnel WB	South Tunnel EB	North Tunnel WB	South Tunnel EB	East Ventilation Building				West Ventilation Building				East Ventilation Building				West Ventilation Building						
Time					Supply		Exhaust		Supply		Exhaust		Supply		Exhaust		Supply		Exhaust				
					1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	5	6	7	
14:00					N	L	N	N	L	N	N	N	N	N	N	L	L	N	N	N	L	N	N
15:00	1313	1456																					
	1250	1792	16	13																			
16:00																							
	1098	1448																					
17:00																							
	904	1406	16	9																			
18:00																							
	2310		12	10																			

Time	Beginning Shift 10:13's	EP: +45DEG 4/5	WP: +49DEG Cldy 4/5
13:45	Relieved "C" crew, 50 mph both tunnels, EVB NT Sup & Ex 600s T, reservoir 12'2", "Wat 4 Rox" "St Gr" "Trkr Spd 35" exit NT, OHs enabled, 213e VMS offline, E & W emer equip checked, MB#10 offline		
14:37	Trigg & Hemphill into NT supply duct to insulate downspout Sg. #156-#157./ 1450 Glycol recycled SW boiler rm, 1 bag btrash to dumpster		
15:08	EB hazmat Rawhide trk 12k Flam3 Ut 966ZR Mr. Northstrom denied./ 1530 S.Ludolph fini gather trash EVB fan deck & 10-42, 1qt oil #70003732./		
18:08	LRR occupied MB #1 NT & Chain Station overview per JOA disp. 1qt oil/ 1826 906 10-42		
18:36 W5	*Semi stoppage NT R/L Zn#6, WB held, Quintana Trigg enroute./ *1841 WB ris 5mins, pulled out E. Wrecker, Platinum trk II P947242, Blown radiator hose./		
19:30	2 persons clr EVB NT Supply duct, 600s online./ 1945 B. Trigg 10-42./ 1940 R. Hemphill & J. Quintana pulling WB AWS barrels R. shoulder to median, & hookup to solar arrow bd trl		

Tunnel logs Eisenhower Tunnel

Colorado DOT Tunnel Data

IBM Cognos – Colorado Traffic Management System

- Launched in 2013
- Reporting, Analysis and Event Management
- 4 Major Transportation Management Centers (TMCs)
 - ❖ Colorado TMC (CTMC) Golden, Hanging Lake Tunnel (HLT TMC), Eisenhower/Johnson Tunnel (EJT TMC) & Colorado Springs (CS TMC).
- *Information collection network*
 - ❖ Detectors and sensors, CCTV cameras, ramp meters, radar detectors, weather stations, National Weather Service, information toll tag readers, and road condition by Colorado State Patrol (CSP) troopers and CDOT maintenance forces
- Our interest: Events associated with Tunnel

CDOT Database

Data Collection

- Search Attributes

REQUIRED PROMPTS			
Date Range for Report	Road Type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Road Click to refresh Road list.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Direction Click to refresh Direction list.
Start Date: <input type="text" value="Jan 1, 2019"/> End Date: <input type="text" value="Oct 10, 2019"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Arterial <input type="checkbox"/> Colorado <input type="checkbox"/> US Highway <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Interstate <input type="checkbox"/> No Road Type tied to Event Select all Deselect all	<input type="checkbox"/> I 225 <input type="checkbox"/> I 25 <input type="checkbox"/> I 270 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> I 70 <input type="checkbox"/> I 76 Select all Deselect all	<input type="checkbox"/> North <input type="checkbox"/> South <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> East <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> West Select all Deselect all

OPTIONAL PROMPTS						
Event Type Only choose if you want to RESTRICT the Event Types pulled into report.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Event Sub-Type Click to display list of Event Sub-Types based on Event Type.	Classification	Roadway Closure	Mile Marker Range	Flags	Day of Week
<input type="checkbox"/> Chain law <input type="checkbox"/> Emergency Alert <input type="checkbox"/> Event Response <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Incident <input type="checkbox"/> Managed Lane Event <input type="checkbox"/> PSA <input type="checkbox"/> Planned Event <input type="checkbox"/> Roadwork <input type="checkbox"/> Special Event Select all Deselect all	<input type="checkbox"/> Abandoned Vehicle <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accident <input type="checkbox"/> Accident Investigation Wo <input type="checkbox"/> Avalanche <input type="checkbox"/> Avalanche Control <input type="checkbox"/> Blocked <input type="checkbox"/> Bridge Work <input type="checkbox"/> Closed Select all Deselect all	<input type="checkbox"/> Minimal <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe Select all Deselect all	<input type="checkbox"/> Alternating Traffic <input type="checkbox"/> CMV Restriction <input type="checkbox"/> Full Closure <input type="checkbox"/> No Information Available <input type="checkbox"/> No Lanes Closed <input type="checkbox"/> Partial Closure <input type="checkbox"/> Planned Closure Select all Deselect all	MM Start <input type="text" value="213"/> MM End <input type="text" value="215"/>	CMV Flag <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Yes Hazmat Flag <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Yes Fatality Flag <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Monday <input type="checkbox"/> Tuesday <input type="checkbox"/> Wednesday <input type="checkbox"/> Thursday <input type="checkbox"/> Friday <input type="checkbox"/> Saturday <input type="checkbox"/> Sunday <input type="checkbox"/> Holiday Select all Deselect all

Typical Data from Cognos

Event ID	Road	Direction	Roadway Closure	Location	Event Type	Event Sub Type	Event Sub Class	MM Start	MM End	Event Severity	Event Start Date	Event End Date	Partial Closure Duration	Full Closure Duration	Total Duration
227323	I 70	West	Full Closure	Eisenhower Tunnel	Incident	Accident	Single Vehicle	215	215	Severe	Nov 30, 2015 8:36:00 AM	Nov 30, 2015 9:00:00 AM		21 minutes	24 minutes
227585	I 70	East (BOTH)	No Lanes Closed	East vail to Eisenhower Tunnel	Chain law	Chain Law Code 15		184	213.5	Moderate	Dec 5, 2015 8:47:00 AM	Dec 5, 2015 10:05:00 AM			1 hour 18 minutes
227604	I 70	West	No Information Available	Eisenhower Tunnel	Incident	Emergency Roadwork		213		Severe	Dec 6, 2015 1:16:00 AM	Dec 6, 2015 3:15:00 AM			1 hour 59 minutes
227611	I 70	East	Partial Closure	Eisenhower Tunnel	Planned Event	Road Work	Roadway	213	213	Moderate	Dec 6, 2015 9:49:00 PM	Dec 7, 2015 4:38:00 AM	6 hours 49 minutes		6 hours 49 minutes
227637	I 70	East	Partial Closure, Partial Closure	Eisenhower Tunnel	Planned Event	Road Work	Roadway	213	213	Moderate	Dec 7, 2015 8:20:00 PM	Dec 8, 2015 5:36:00 AM	10 hours 34 minutes		9 hours 16 minutes
227639	I 70	East	Full Closure	Eisenhower Tunnel	Incident	Safety Closure		213	213	Severe	Dec 7, 2015 9:57:00 PM	Dec 7, 2015 10:15:00 PM		8 minutes	18 minutes
227640	I 70	East	Full Closure	Eisenhower Tunnel	Incident	Safety Closure		213	213	Minimal	Dec 8, 2015 12:07:00 AM	Dec 8, 2015 2:16:00 AM		2 hours 9 minutes	2 hours 9 minutes
227669	I 70	East	Partial Closure, Partial Closure	Eisenhower Tunnel	Planned Event	Road Work	Roadway	213	213	Moderate	Dec 8, 2015 8:00:00 PM	Dec 9, 2015 3:14:00 AM	11 hours 54 minutes		7 hours 14 minutes
227727	I 70	East	Partial Closure, Partial Closure	Eisenhower Tunnel	Planned Event	Road Work	Roadway	213	213	Moderate	Dec 9, 2015 8:00:00 PM	Dec 10, 2015 8:38:00 AM	16 hours 56 minutes		12 hours 38 minutes
227835	I 70	East	Partial Closure	Eisenhower Tunnel	Planned Event	Road Work	Roadway	213	215	Moderate	Dec 10, 2015 7:58:00 PM	Dec 11, 2015 3:26:00 AM	7 hours 27 minutes		7 hours 28 minutes
227874	I 70	West (BOTH)	No Lanes Closed	Dotsero to Morrison	Weather Event	Warning	Heavy Snow Warning	133	259	Minimal	Dec 11, 2015 4:52:00 PM	Dec 11, 2015 9:29:00 PM			4 hours 37 minutes
227882	I 70	West (BOTH)	No Lanes Closed	Dotsero to Morrison	Weather Event	Warning	Heavy Snow Warning	133	259	Minimal	Dec 11, 2015 9:44:00 PM	Dec 12, 2015 2:19:00 PM			16 hours 35 minutes
227903	I 70	West (BOTH)	No Lanes Closed	Silverthorne to Eisenhower Tunnel	Chain law	Chain Law Code 15		205	213	Moderate	Dec 12, 2015 5:25:00 AM	Dec 12, 2015 12:05:00 PM			6 hours 40 minutes

Eisenhower Tunnel Data

Event Types – 9

- Chain Law - 3 sub types
- Event Response - 4 sub types
- **Incident** – 35 sub types
- System Maintenance – 3 sub types
- **Planned Event** – 3 sub types
- Public safety announcement – 10 sub types
- **Road Work** – 7 sub types
- Special Event – 2 sub types
- Weather – 11 sub types

Event Sub Types – 78

Eisenhower Tunnel Data

Records

- 2013 onwards
- 3944 Events

Important Event Types

- Incident – 1607 events
- Planned Event – 645 events

Tunnel	Events	# of Events	Event Sub Type	# of Events Sub Type	Partial Closure		Full Closure	
					# of Closures	Total Time (mins)	# of Closures	Total Time (mins)
Eisenhower Tunnel	Chain Law	1264	Code 15	359	1	15	-	-
	Incident	1607	Spun Out	32	24	907	3	137
			Snow Removal operation	117	15	4774	-	-
			Safety Metering	31	-	-	1	10
			Safety Closure	103	2	444	90	12004
			Outside Agency Activity	17	2	86	3	32
			Mechanical	101	46	1956	16	408
			Abandoned Vehicle	6	2	338	-	-
			Environmental	41	7	122	5	1384
			Heavy Traffic	533	10	1534	1	43
			Accident	111	33	1546	47	3775
			Emergency Roadwork	34	13	2483	2	74
			Continuous Flow Metering	121	-	-	1	48
			Debris	27	3	51	-	-
			Planned Event	645	Blasting	2	2	1221
	Avalanche Control	36			1	25	17	1427
	Road Work	607			419	380487	14	16415
	Public safety announcement	245	Safety	77	-	-	1	63
			Road Condition	27	-	-	1	25
			Environmental	13	-	-	1	28
Special Event	2	State Occasion	1	-	-	1	25	

Event Reports - Example

Report

- Event ID
- I-70 WB
- *Planned Event*
- *Partial Closure – Right Lane*
- *Tunnel Maintenance*
- *Cleaning Cameras*
- *29 minutes*

Event ID: 249414										Event Type: Planned Event	
Event Description											
Update Date		Description									
Feb 11, 2017 12:38:48 AM		Right lane closed for tunnel maintenance									
Notes: Tunnel maintenance - cleaning cameras											
Status:	Clear	Sub Type:	Road Work	Severity:	Moderate	Start Time:	Feb 11, 2017 12:36:00 AM	Location:	I 70 West (MM 215 - 215)	Classification:	None
Clear Time:	Feb 11, 2017 1:05:00 AM	Location Desc:	Eisenhower Tunnel	Source:	CDOT	Last Update:	Feb 11, 2017 1:05:42 AM	Roadway Name:	I 70	CMV:	Unknown
Event Duration:	29 minutes	Type Roadway Closure:	Partial Closure	HazMat Load:	Unknown	Security Group:	Eisenhower Tunnel	Lane Control:		Fatality:	Unknown
Location Audit											
Start Date	End Date	Road	MM Start	MM End	Direction	Sub-Type	Sub-Class	Road Closure			
Feb 11, 2017 12:38:40 AM	Feb 11, 2017 1:05:41 AM	I 70	215	215	West	Road Work	Roadway	Partial Closure			
VTMS Messaging											
ID	Device Name	User Name	Message				Start Date	End Date			
5026	070W217 LOVELAND PASS	morrellk	RIGHT LANE CLOSED 1 MILE AHEAD MOVE OVER FOR CREWS				Feb 11, 2017 12:39:01 AM	Feb 11, 2017 1:06:02 AM			
5026	070W217 LOVELAND PASS	morrellk	BLANK				Feb 11, 2017 1:06:02 AM	Feb 11, 2017 3:29:45 AM			
Call Log Data											
Call Log ID	Call Date	Type Call Log Desc	Type Call Log Agency Desc	Type Call Log Direction Desc	Comments	Security Group Name	Create User	Contact Name			
111075	Feb 11, 2017 12:35:00 AM	Call	CDOT		Tunnel maintenance - cleaning cameras	Eisenhower Tunnel	morrellk	Control Desk Vince			
111077	Feb 11, 2017 1:04:00 AM	Call	CDOT	In-Bound	Work complete	Eisenhower Tunnel	morrellk	Control Desk			

Data Analysis – Identify Major Events

Till Date

- 1314 Events
- 50% Maintenance & Repair events
- 20% Partial Closure of total time (365 days in 5 years)
- 30 days of Full closure (5 year period)

Type of Event	Number of Events	Partial Closure		Full Closure		Closure per Event
		mins	%	mins	%	mins
Maintenance & Repair	677	436827	83.1	24653	57.0	359.0
Accident	231	2508	0.5	11151	25.8	53.7
Road Work	123	72833	13.9	24	0.1	296.3
Snow Removal	135	10419	2.0		0.0	38.6
Disabled Vehicle	71	1483	0.3	253	0.6	14.0
Fire	19	726	0.1	1256	2.9	85.2
Avalanche Control	46	0	0.0	1530	3.5	33.3
Technical / Upgrade	6	720	0.1	4005	9.3	727.5
Closed	6	0	0.0	373	0.9	62.2
Total (mins)	1314	525516	100.0	43245	100.0	232.9
Total (days)		364.94		30.03		
Total %		20.00		1.65		

How to Record and Use data for Tunnel Resilience?

Systematic Quantifiable Data

Quantify Tunnel Functionality

- Simplified Metric to Quantify Functionality
 - ❖ Q is **state of tunnel operation** independent of traffic condition
 - ❖ Simpler metric is easier to record
 - ❖ Functionality Loss: **Area over the curve**
- Cognos Data
 - ❖ Event Type
 - ❖ Period of Closure
 - ❖ Lanes Closed
- Cognos Issues
 - ❖ Speed Limit seldom recorded
 - ❖ Reporting Inconsistent

$$Q = \left(\frac{\text{\# of open lanes}}{\text{Total \# of lanes}} \right) \times \left(\frac{\text{Reduced speed limit}}{\text{Normal speed limit}} \right)$$

Functionality loss versus Time

Module – Physical Process

Example - Hazmat Release

- Trigger – Snowfall
- Snowfall - Loveland Pass Closure
- 10 year Loveland Pass Snow Data
- Eisenhower (EJMT) Tunnel Logs
 - ❖ Closure intervals
 - ❖ Closure Frequency
- *Computation*
 - ❖ *Period of Event*
 - ❖ *Every hour closure frequency*
 - ❖ *Period of each closure*

Hazmat Release - Result

Total Time Loss

- Minimum – 152 minutes / year
- Maximum – 1527 minutes / year
- Mean – 637.6 minutes / year
- Median – 629.5 minutes / year
- Mode – 533 minutes / year
- Std. Dev. – 201.5 minutes / year

Annual Snowfall range 250 to 470 inches per year at Loveland Pass

Event Days (intense snowfall)

- Minimum – 7 days / year
- Maximum – 32 days / year
- Mean – 18.2 days / year
- Median – 18 days / year
- Mode – 16 days / year
- Std. Dev. – 4 days / year

100 year Snowfall Simulation

Summary

- Need to build a systematic Operation and Event Occurrence data collection Framework
- Data record and management systems like Cognos (CDOT) exist
- Need of **Consistent** data records
- Limited data availability at current date
- It is **time consuming** and hard to Retrieve data

Future Work

- Study Complete data
 - ❖ Identify Major Events
 - ❖ Develop Distributions and generate parameters
 - ❖ Expand Framework
- Develop simulation Tool / Model
- Use model to help in Decision Making

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Thank you !

Complete Tunnel Data Framework

